

Open Science Retreat 2025

#OSR25CH

Event Report

April 13-17, 2025

Beatenberg, Switzerland

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Summary at a Glance

The **Open Science Retreat** took place from **April 13 to 17, 2025**, in **Beatenberg, Switzerland**, a quiet alpine village overlooking Lake Thun. The serene natural surroundings provided the perfect backdrop for focused reflection, deep discussions, and meaningful connections.

The retreat brought together an **international group of open science community members**, including researchers, research software engineers, data stewards, librarians, community managers, and advocates from a wide range of disciplines and backgrounds. The participants shared a commitment to improving how research is done and communicated through open, collaborative, and reproducible practices.

We organized this retreat as an opportunity to **step away from the daily grind and reconnect with the purpose and potential of open science**. Our goal was to create a space where participants could reset, recharge, and dive into topics they are passionate about that often get sidelined in the rush of everyday responsibilities. Whether through structured sessions or informal conversations, the retreat, guided by the unconference format, was designed to support creative thinking, peer learning, and community building.

Purpose & Vision

The **Open Science Retreat** was inspired by a shared desire to slow down, reflect, and reconnect with the values and like-minded individuals that drive the open science movement. Many of us working in open and collaborative research environments often face high workloads, fragmented communities, and limited time to step back and think creatively. This retreat was envisioned as a counterbalance—a space to **pause the daily rush and focus on the “why” behind our work**.

Our goals were to create an environment that supports **deep thinking, authentic connection, and shared learning**. We wanted to give participants the freedom to explore ideas they don't usually have time for, to exchange knowledge across disciplines and roles, and to feel re-energized in their commitment to open and reproducible science. By using an unconference-style format and centering care, flexibility, and curiosity, we aimed to create a gathering where participants could shape the experience themselves and bring their full selves to the conversation.

This matters deeply for the open science community. As we strive for more inclusive, transparent, and collaborative research practices, we also need **spaces that support the people**

doing the work—not just the outputs. The retreat responded to this need by offering time to think, connect, and imagine together, helping to build a stronger, more sustainable open science ecosystem.

Who Came Together

The retreat brought together a diverse group of participants, including **44 active attendees** from **11 countries**, representing a wide range of roles across the open science landscape. Participants included researchers, research software engineers, data stewards, community managers, and policy advocates working in fields such as **epidemiology, cancer biology, bioinformatics, neuroscience, psychology, digital cultural heritage, library science, earth science, architecture, economics, and more**. Attendees also spanned a range of career stages—from early-career researchers (ECRs over a third of the attendees) to established leaders in the open science community—creating a dynamic environment where fresh perspectives met seasoned experience.

Professional Background

In addition to the active participants, several attendees were accompanied by **partners (5 persons) and children (three children from 2-11 years old)**, which added to the retreat's warm, inclusive atmosphere. The presence of families and spouses reminded us that open science is a human-centered movement and that creating space for care—both personal and professional—is an essential part of building sustainable communities.

The retreat was jointly organized by the **Digital Research Academy**, the **University of Zurich Center for Reproducible Science**, and the **Open Innovation in Life Sciences Association**. We are grateful for the generous support from our sponsors: the **Swiss National Open Research Data Strategy Council**, **Wikimedia CH**, **Imming Impact**, and the **Scientific Exchange grant from the SNSF**, all of whom share a commitment to advancing open and collaborative research.

Participants were selected through an application process designed to ensure a thoughtful and inclusive mix of voices. Applicants were asked to share their motivations for attending the retreat, provide information about their professional background, and indicate their current career stage. An **international selection committee** reviewed and scored the applications based on the applicant's fit with the retreat's purpose and their potential to contribute meaningfully to the shared environment. The final selection aimed to balance international representation, career stages, and disciplinary diversity, with a strong focus on cultivating an open, welcoming, and generative space for all attendees.

What Happened

Program structure

The retreat took place over five days, with a flexible structure designed to balance focused discussions, creative exploration, and unstructured time. In the weeks leading up to the event, participants were virtually introduced to each other on **Mattermost**, an open-source team chat platform, where they began connecting, sharing interests, and proposing unconference session topics. These contributions helped shape the retreat's flow while preserving space for spontaneous ideas and evolving discussions on site.

Participants arrived on the first day and were welcomed with a relaxed orientation session in the late afternoon, followed by informal networking activities throughout the evening to get to know one another. On the morning of the second day, the group reviewed the unconference topics that had been proposed in advance via the Mattermost platform. Together, they selected the themes they were most interested in exploring, forming topic groups based on shared interests. These groups began their collaborative work that same afternoon, setting the tone for a participant-driven retreat where curiosity, initiative, and peer exchange shaped the experience.

Each day followed a gentle rhythm, beginning with a post-breakfast check-in and followed by another after lunch. These short gatherings offered space for topic groups to share progress updates and for participants to propose impromptu short sessions based on emerging questions, shared interests, or spontaneous ideas. The core of each day was structured around morning and afternoon blocks, which participants could use flexibly—for topic group work, short sessions, mentoring appointments, reflective walks, or informal conversations. Evenings concluded with a collective wrap-up and relaxed social activities, creating opportunities to connect and unwind. This daily flow encouraged both focus and fluidity, helping to build an atmosphere of trust, curiosity, and co-creation. On the final day, a closing plenary brought everyone together as topic groups and short sessions shared informal presentations of what they had explored and any outputs or insights that had emerged during the retreat.

In addition to the participant-driven sessions, the retreat also offered two optional workshops designed to strengthen participants' soft skills. One focused on effective negotiation techniques, while the other offered practical guidance for improving grant proposals. These sessions complemented the collaborative work and gave attendees tools they could immediately apply to their careers and ongoing projects.

Topic groups

Topic groups were self-organized teams formed around shared interests, based on the unconference proposals collected before the retreat. Each group explored a specific theme in

depth over several days, with the flexibility to define their own goals, workflows, and outputs. Below are the summaries from each topic group.

Open Science as Labour + Political Activism

Open Science has been and will be political. Participants in this group shared their work in Open Science and other activist contexts. They identified how promoting Open Science can be frustrating and lead to "activist burnout". This group designed a Zine that illustrates a meerkat's journey through Open Science advocacy as many of them have experienced it.

Zines have been a classic medium for distributing political activism information - free to copy and share and expand. This group wanted to highlight how Open Science - like all political work - is inherently a communal effort and that people need to support each other if they want to make a change.

Send this Zine to your students, print it out for your next conference, make your own!

Work in progress: make a version that is easily editable to facilitate translation into different languages.

DOI: 10.53962/t3zn-teda

Preregistration

Creating effective preregistrations can be challenging—especially for those new to the process. While templates and platforms offer support, they must ensure preregistrations are:

1. **Accessible**
2. **Reproducible**
3. **Machine-readable**

To improve current resources, the working group evaluated the PRP-QUANT Template (Bosnjak et al., 2022) and identified areas for improvement. These insights are being used to develop an improved version of the template, as well as a simplified version focused on accessibility. Both will be integrated into the next release of ZPID's preregistration platform, **PreReg**.

The group also addressed a broader issue: in many research communities, preregistration is still uncommon. To help these communities get started, a "**Preregistration Starter Pack**" is in development. Based on the PRP-QUANT Template, it will guide the creation of new, discipline-specific templates. The pack will be hosted on a dedicated website, offering easy access for working groups across fields.

How to Truly Reward OS Practices

This group set out to **reverse-engineer reward systems for Open Science (OS)**. Rather than simply urging institutions and funders to reward OS practices, the group—composed of OS enthusiasts from around the world—took a hands-on, reflective approach.

They began by defining **personas**, representing different roles within the research ecosystem. Next, they mapped out their daily tasks and linked them to the OS practices they actually engage in. This exercise led to a key question: **Which of these practices should be recognized and rewarded—and how?**

During this process, it became clear that **not all OS practices are equally rewardable**, and some may not need explicit rewards at all, as they fall under the umbrella of simply doing good research.

The group then explored **existing rewards** for these practices and brainstormed **new, creative ways** to recognize contributions. All findings were compiled into a **Primer**, which includes:

- Brief bios and AI-generated avatars of the personas
- A description of the group's process
- A list of OS practices and the corresponding rewards—both existing and proposed

A placeholder entry has been created on **Zenodo** [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15235058], where the finalized document will be published after copy-editing. The goal is to enable others to adapt this method to include additional roles and perspectives in the Open Science ecosystem.

Sharing + Marketing Open Science Initiatives

This group set out to explore the **outreach landscape for Open Science** across various international contexts. The goal was to identify **barriers to promoting Open Science** and to suggest possible strategies to overcome them.

As part of this effort, the group:

- Compiled an **initial list of outreach resources** relevant to Open Science promotion
- Conducted a **pilot survey** to gather insights into the outreach environment, which confirmed that many of the anticipated barriers are indeed being experienced by respondents
- Reflected on their own experience providing **outreach support** to Open Science advocates who participated in the **2025 Open Science Retreat**

These combined efforts helped lay the groundwork for better understanding and improving how Open Science is communicated and supported globally.

Open Research Data (ORD) Reuse

This unconference group focused on identifying the **challenges and opportunities related to the reuse of Open Research Data (ORD)**.

Their work included:

- Mapping the landscape of **teaching and training initiatives** focused on data reuse
- Collecting **use cases and success stories** that highlight successful ORD reuse
- Reviewing **funding calls** that specifically support projects reusing ORD

Looking ahead, the group plans to continue gathering relevant resources and begin exploring **minimal information standards** that support data reusability. This next phase will be carried out as part of a **Swiss-Dutch collaborative initiative**.

Assessing Open Science

This group drafted a preprint proposing **concrete assessment examples** to support the teaching of open and reproducible science. While numerous resources exist for curricula and lesson plans, there appears to be no centralized collection of ideas for **assessing open science competencies**. The preprint addresses this gap by outlining a series of example assessments developed by the group, along with references to additional relevant materials.

The preprint is available here: https://osf.io/preprints/osf/jb72d_v1

Even More Open Research

Believing that the future of research can be improved by becoming “even more open,” this group mapped existing open tools and workflows across the research lifecycle to identify gaps in current practices. They collected over 100 tools and developed a [prototype website \(https://www.advansci-research.com/resourcelist\)](https://www.advansci-research.com/resourcelist) to showcase them. Building on this foundation, the group outlined an ambitious plan for future work, including a position paper (working title: “*10 Simple Things Needed for the Future of Science*”) and a grant proposal, to be submitted to OSCARS in May 2025.

Survey Says: Open Science Game

This unconference group developed a game to raise awareness about open science in a lighthearted way. Their goal was to share all resources and information needed to play the game on R+, enabling others to reuse it locally.

The game is based on the Family Feud format. To prepare, the group created a survey, collected data, developed all materials needed to play, and organized a dry run during the three-day retreat. They collected 77 survey responses in just 1.5 days and successfully conducted the dry

run with retreat participants. The experience was enjoyable and provided valuable feedback on the game setup. Based on this, the group made several improvements and created a package to make the game openly available.

Short Sessions

Short sessions were participant-led discussions or hands-on activities proposed during the daily check-ins. They provided a flexible space for spontaneous ideas, niche topics, skill-sharing, or open questions that didn't require the time commitment of a full topic group.

Bridging Research - New Digital Roles

The discussion focused on defining and strengthening roles at the intersection of research and support under the umbrella term eResearch. Participants emphasized the need for standardized job titles and clear, accessible job descriptions that bridge the traditional divide between scientific and support roles. Visibility and marketing were seen as key to showcasing the value of these positions. The group called for integrated staffing models, the creation of viable and attractive career paths, and continuous training opportunities. Overarching goals include attracting and retaining talent, improving role visibility, and addressing structural barriers such as closed systems and opaque job language.

Role Clarity and Standardization

- Standardized job titles (e.g., Open Science Officer, eScientist, RSE, Data Steward, Data Scientist, Embedded Librarian)
- Clear and appropriate job descriptions
- Avoiding closed/off-putting language or "hidden curricula"
- Bridging the divide between research and service functions

Visibility and Value Recognition

- Marketing of roles to demonstrate their impact and value
- Enhancing visibility of eResearch roles within and beyond institutions

Organizational Integration

- possibly beneficial: a central staff model with integrated roles rather than divided support

Career Development and Retention

- Established and recognized career paths
- Incentives to stay in these roles (e.g., recognition, stability)
- Continuous professional development (CPD) with credits or certificates
- Engaging with students to introduce and expand these career pathways early on

Strategic Goals

- Talent attraction: making roles appealing and accessible
- Talent retention: providing meaningful incentives and growth
- Addressing systemic barriers: closed systems, unclear language, and lack of visibility

Nanopubs: A Spark of Potential at the Open Science Retreat

This short session introduced [nanopubs](#) to a small group of participants at the Open Science retreat, and sparked a lively discussion around their current state and future possibilities. A key takeaway was the significant lack of awareness surrounding nanopubs within the community. Participants were largely unfamiliar with the concept, highlighting a critical barrier to adoption. Beyond awareness, understanding was also limited. We explored the core idea of nanopubs as small, versioned, and digitally signed assertions, building blocks for more complex knowledge. The discussion quickly moved to the potential of nanopubs to enable assertion chains, facilitate the creation of dynamic knowledge graphs, and leverage semantic web technologies like CiTO (Citation Typing Ontology) to provide richer context and traceability to research findings. However, this potential felt theoretical. A recurring theme throughout the session was the desperate need for practical examples, readily available tutorials, concrete use cases demonstrating nanopub implementation, and comprehensive documentation. The absence of these resources apparently hinders experimentation and understanding. Despite these challenges, the group was enthusiastic about the promise of nanopubs. We agreed that showcasing tangible benefits – like improved reproducibility or more efficient knowledge discovery – would be vital for driving wider adoption.

How to Start your Open Science Community

In this session, OS Retreat participant Melanie Imming presented the activities and structure of the International Network of Open Science Communities (OSC). Participants from various local communities also shared their experiences in establishing OSCs and strategies for engaging people in their initiatives.

Link: <https://osc-international.com/>

Creativity & How it Fits into our Work

In this spontaneous 50-minute session, participants explored how creativity integrates with their research work. A key insight was that the rigor, rules, and evidence-based nature of research do not exclude creativity; rather, a balance between structure and open creativity tends to be more effective than strict rules or unstructured freedom alone. They discussed how constraints can actually enhance creativity and considered the idea of recognizing which rules might be worth challenging. Finally, the group reflected on ways to cultivate more space for creativity by paying attention to their own needs and conditions for creative thinking.

The workshop focused on reframing negotiation as a dance rather than a battle (though participants were welcome to bring their own style). Key topics and practices included:

- ① **Dance to the rhythm** – understanding the importance of timing, such as engaging before budget decisions are finalized to avoid pushback like “Oh, the budget’s already set.”
- ② **Own the floor** – moving beyond simply listing completed tasks to reflecting on the broader impact of one’s work, preparing participants to advocate effectively.
- ③ **Know the basic 3-step** – a straightforward framework designed to build credibility, make compelling requests, and provide negotiation partners with concrete points to respond to.
- ④ **Dance with, not against** – embracing collaboration by balancing assertiveness with cooperativeness.
- ⑤ **Curious, not furious** – developing resilience to respond to pushback with curiosity and creative problem-solving.

Above all, the workshop encouraged participants to have fun while honing these skills.

Open Research at the Grant-Writing Stage

This session explored how openness can be integrated into the earliest stages of the research process—specifically during grant writing. Facilitated by Joseph Corneli, the workshop aimed to contribute to the evidence base around openness in early-stage research. It included two practical components: (1) a “sandpit” exercise for idea exchange and collaboration on grant concepts, and (2) a structured “writers’ workshop” to provide feedback on draft proposals.

The session began with a short introduction to the objectives and format of the workshop. Participants then split into small groups to discuss and refine ideas for open research-related grant proposals. These ideas had either been shared prior to the session or were generated during the retreat. Each group selected one idea to bring forward to the next part of the workshop.

Following a brief comfort break, the second half of the session focused on a **writers’ workshop** format. The group discussed three selected proposals, spending 20 minutes on each. Each discussion followed a consistent structure: a brief presentation of the idea, a review of its strengths, suggestions for improvement, and time for clarifying questions. The format encouraged constructive feedback and peer learning.

The session provided a structured space for participants to exchange ideas and develop their grant-writing practice through open, collaborative methods. It also highlighted opportunities to make the grant application process itself more transparent and participatory.

Networking Session on Open Research Data

This Session, organised by the Swiss National ORD Strategy Council (StraCo) representatives, was designed to foster connection and dialogue between StraCo and participants by tackling bite-sized challenges grounded in the national ORD strategy. Participants rotated through discussion-based “missions,” using prompts to explore key topics such as the definition and diversity of research data, the balance between openness and protection, and the integration of ORD into research culture and education. To move between stations we listened to yodeling music and walked around until the music stopped. The interactive format sparked a range of responses - from insightful reflections to moments of confusion or critique - highlighting both enthusiasm and ongoing challenges around ORD implementation. Popular challenges like defining “research data” showed the rich disciplinary variety in interpretations, while more complex tasks, such as justifying limits to data sharing, revealed a need for deeper guidance and reframing. Across topics, recurring themes emerged: the importance of community-building, the gap between support structures and researchers’ everyday realities, and the desire for pragmatic, sustainable ORD practices. The session did not only encourage creative engagement but hopefully also generated valuable input for refining strategy and support mechanisms moving forward.

Highlights & Reflections

The retreat was full of memorable moments that reflected the spirit of open science: collaborative, joyful, and deeply human. We experienced *all* the seasons over the course of the week—from snowy mornings to sunny hikes—adding to the cozy, unexpected charm of the gathering.

Each day offered something special beyond the sessions. Mornings began with **participant-led yoga** and **jogs through the mountain landscape**, setting an energizing tone. Evenings brought laughter and connection: **slide karaoke**, **silent discos**, a **face mask pampering night**, a spontaneous **arm-wrestling contest**, and lots of shared **slogans and dances** celebrating open science.

Participants also went on scenic hikes, swam in the panoramic pool hall, and enjoyed plenty of downtime to rest or explore. Whether through lively group discussions or quiet moments in nature, the retreat offered space to recharge, reflect, and build community.

Photo moments by [Jazelle Carillo](#)

Interactive Agenda Wall

Unconference Topic Selection

Networking Activity:

Working together to tackle Open Research Data-themed mini-challenges & Dancing to a good Swiss yodel

Open Science Participants in the wild (group hike)

Slide Karaoke Night

Silent Disco and Arm Wrestling

Survey Says Game Night

New Snow Day participant and Snow Group photo (by DRA)

Final Presentations

Fostering Community & Inclusion

From the very beginning, the retreat emphasized creating a welcoming, safe, and inclusive space for all participants. During the orientation on the first day, we introduced not only the retreat structure but also clearly shared our **house rules and Code of Conduct**. A designated **Code of Conduct Committee** was in place and visible throughout the retreat to ensure a supportive environment where everyone could feel respected and heard.

Accessibility was a central consideration in the retreat’s planning. The venue was selected with **physical accessibility in mind**, offering features like ramps and an elevator for those with limited mobility. During registration, participants were asked if they required **any accommodations (e.g. physical, cognitive, or social)**, so that the organizing team could provide appropriate support ahead of time.

To foster **connection and communication**, we combined analog and digital tools. A **hand-written, interactive schedule** in the main room served as a living hub where participants could easily check updates or add short sessions. Online, we used **Mattermost**, an open-source team chat platform, to help everyone stay connected and coordinate informally throughout the week.

From structured topic groups to spontaneous social events, every aspect of the retreat was designed to balance openness with care—making it easy to participate meaningfully, connect authentically, and feel part of a vibrant, inclusive open science community.

Participant Feedback

Feedback on the Venue

Participants overwhelmingly appreciated the **stunning mountain location**, describing the views as beautiful and the environment as peaceful, quiet, and conducive to both focus and relaxation. Many highlighted the **venue's comfort, cleanliness, and friendly staff**, as well as the **quality of the food and communal meal setup**. The setting struck a balance between **being immersed in nature while still accessible to nearby towns**, which added to the overall experience. Attendees also valued the **opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and practical workshops**. While a few noted the desire for more connected common spaces or a venue exclusively for retreat participants, the overall sentiment reflected a deep appreciation for the calming atmosphere, scenic surroundings, and thoughtful structure of the event.

What should we do again?

Participants consistently highlighted the retreat's friendly, inclusive, and laid-back environment, with special appreciation for the diversity of attendees and the intentional welcome extended to partners and families. The **unconference format**, with its balance of structured and unstructured time, was widely praised for allowing flexibility, creativity, and self-direction. Many noted the value of the **collaborative topic groups, practical workshops, and facilitated social activities** like slide karaoke and the silent disco, which helped build community in a low-pressure environment. The **full board setup and shared meals** created natural opportunities for connection, and participants valued the **intentional breaks, recreation time, and beautiful surroundings** for enabling both focus and rest. Overall, the retreat was seen as a rare space that blended productivity with joy, learning, and genuine community-building.

What could we have done better

While the retreat was widely praised, participants offered constructive suggestions to further enhance the experience. A recurring theme was the **desire for a more unified venue**—ideally where all participants stay in the same building and the retreat has exclusive use of the space—to foster casual interactions. Some also wished for **more comfortable or homey common areas** for informal hangouts. A few noted **logistical challenges**, such as early departures due to travel schedules, and suggested extending the retreat by a day or adjusting the final day's timing to accommodate wrap-ups without conflict.

In terms of programming, several attendees requested **more downtime**, fewer overlapping sessions, and perhaps a **small number of structured talks or introductory sessions** on open science topics to complement the unconference format—particularly to support newcomers. Suggestions also included increasing time for group introductions, offering **more practical or**

tool-oriented content, and creating **better communication infrastructure**, such as a physical board to supplement the Mattermost chat.

Other ideas included **clearer food labeling and more vegan options**, **bringing your own name badges**, and **including more diverse voices**, such as citizen scientists and underrepresented fields. Despite these notes, feedback reflected a deep appreciation for the retreat, with several participants noting that many improvements were already in motion or simply “wishful thinking.”

Based on the constructive feedback, here are several actionable steps we can take to improve the next Open Science Retreat:

Venue & Environment

- Social spaces - select a venue with more casual, cozy hangout areas for spontaneous conversations and downtime
- Meeting Spaces - more meeting rooms to accommodate more topics/short sessions

Retreat Structure & Scheduling

- Extend retreat by one night or adjust the final day’s schedule to allow full participation in closing activities without travel conflicts
- Include more unstructured time to rest, reflect, or have impromptu sessions
- Consider fewer mandatory check-ins or offer optional progress updates to reduce session fatigue; on the same note, try to not schedule so many parallel sessions.

Sessions & Content

- Include **introductory or orientation sessions** on Open Science topics, especially for newcomers. Perhaps build it into an icebreaker event.
- Introduce “**meet the partners**” or **welcome circles** early on to integrate partners and families.

Food & Amenities

- Improve availability of **vegan and dietary-specific meals**.
- Consider small touches like **welcome coffee/snacks upon arrival**.
- Encourage participants to **bring reusable name badges** for sustainability and fun.

Inclusion & Representation

- **Reach out to underrepresented fields and roles** in Open Science, including citizen scientists and non-academics.
- Maintain a **diverse mix of career stages and geographic backgrounds**, and continue refining the selection process to support this balance.

Outcomes & What's Next

The retreat sparked and strengthened several exciting collaborations. One standout example is the **Swiss-Dutch collaboration on Open Research Data (ORD)**, which began during the retreat and continues beyond it. The group is actively collecting, curating, and sharing ORD resources, building momentum for cross-border cooperation in open science.

Many of the ideas, plans, and outputs developed during the retreat are openly available through a dedicated [ResearchEquals collection](https://www.researchequals.com/collections/k86g-wf) (<https://www.researchequals.com/collections/k86g-wf>). These living documents include workshop notes, topic group outcomes, and community reflections—offering a transparent and reusable resource for the broader open science ecosystem. We'll highlight a few of these in this section to spotlight the creativity and collaborative spirit of the retreat.

Looking ahead, the energy from this retreat will carry into future events and community-building efforts. We were thrilled to introduce the **new organizing team for the next Open Science Retreat**, which is planned to take place in the **UK in 2026 (#OSR26UK)**.

Communication & Outreach

Sharing & Marketing in Real Time

During the retreat, a topic group on *Sharing & Marketing Open Science Initiatives* formed a sub-group that walked the talk—crafting and posting real-time social media updates via the channels of the DRA (LinkedIn, Mastodon, BlueSky) about the retreat's workshops, topic groups, and community moments. These posts helped broaden the reach of the retreat beyond those physically present, and also included dedicated posts to thank our generous sponsors.

The LinkedIn posts generated 13,647 impressions in the week of the event and up to a week after the event (April 13 - 24, 2025), with 8152 impressions during the retreat days. The post engagement rates during this time period ranged between 6.5%-44.2%. Follower growth on LinkedIn significantly increased by 140 during this time period as well. Below are some of the most popular posts by impression and engagement rate.

Pre-Retreat Promotion & Media Mentions

Leading up to the retreat, we ran a series of posts to promote registration and build excitement—many of which were cross-posted and amplified across networks. Notably, the retreat was also featured on the **EOSC website** as a highlighted Open Science event (<https://eossc.eu/events/open-science-retreat/>). Before, during and after the retreat, participants shared their reflections and favorite moments on personal channels, helping to spread the retreat's energy across the global Open Science community.

Lisa Spitzer @lispitzer.bsky.social · 1mo
Can't wait to join the Open Science Retreat organized by @digiresacademy.bsky.social next week! 🎉 I'm super excited to dive into whole a week focusing on #OpenScience, connect with amazing people, and collaborate on some awesome projects! #OSR2025

1 comment 1 share 7 likes

Emily Nordmann @emilynordmann.bsky.social · 1mo
The retreat format was an incredible reminder that to get stuff done you just need to make time for it. James, Gaby and I have written a full 3000 word paper from scratch essentially two days and about 10 hours (we're just waiting for the preprint approval and it will be shared!).

2 comments 2 likes

James Bartlett @bartlettje.bsky.social · 1mo
Four seasons in four days! Absolutely wonderful time at #OSR25CH hosted by @digiresacademy.bsky.social.

Emily Nordmann @emilynordmann.bsky.social · 1mo
When I say that #OSR25CF gave us everything, I really mean it.

Day 1 - Day 4 🥰

2 shares 6 likes

Ryssa Moffat @ryssamoffat.bsky.social · 27d
 ✨🖌️ The final meerkat sketches are ready!
 Straight from the Open Science Retreat #OSR25 in 🇨🇦
 1/8

OPEN SCIENCE IS POLITICAL

OPENSOURCE
 A GUIDE TO
 RECOVERY FOR
 ACTIVIST BURNOUT

2 16 30

Lydia Riedl @lydia-riedl.bsky.social · 1mo
 This was again an interesting event #OSR25CH with amazingly interesting outcomes (doi.org/10.53962/k86...) and even more interesting weather...

2 7

Christian Meesters
 @rupdecat@fediscience.org

Reflecting about "retreats".

I recently attended the Open Science Retreat. And wonder, how I can possibly keep up the spirit for myself? As @HeidiSeibold keeps rightfully reminding participants – a retreat is there to "recharge your batteries". Yep. And why is this necessary (for me)? Simply because I work too much and care too less? Imposed deadlines? The course system? Toxic work environments? It adds up.

For me, it starts with the morning rush (family! school!) and continues thereafter. And yet, should I lament? No!

Well, I know too many good researchers leaving academia because they were either "burned out" or suffering from the work place (plus the fight for tenure). The usual. Right?

Basically, there is little to do. It just took me from grad student to this time to acknowledge, that I needed to change my work pattern and get away from people who despise my science (yes, I was working too much amongst physicists looking down on life scientists). Confining myself to working with people I like is not easy, but does wonders for me.

Then, what are we going to do about it? At least we should discuss our science utopia and draw conclusions every once or while! A good starting point might be researchequals.com/modules/tbp... by @da5nsy - even though my difficulties and hence my point of view is different.

My retreat resolution? To start blogging again. Sometimes with reflections on (Open) Science. You do not have to read those posts! 😊

www.researchequals.com
Research in 2050
 A blog post summarising discussions from the Open Science Ret...

#osr25ch #AcademicChatter

Apr 19, 2025, 11:05 AM · Web

Last edited Apr 22, 10:09 AM

2 boosts · 4 favorites

Sustaining Visibility of the Outcomes

We'll continue to share outputs from the retreat through the ResearchEquals Collection, where topic groups and individuals are publishing their collaborative work. The Digital Research Academy will keep highlighting new contributions via social media as they're released.

Gratitude

We're deeply grateful to everyone who made this year's Open Science Retreat a success—our brilliant **participants**, generous **workshop leaders**, thoughtful **facilitators**, supportive **funders**, dedicated **volunteers**, and incredible **local organizing team**. Every conversation, question, shared laugh, and new connection contributed to the warm, collaborative energy that defined the week.

A special thanks to our **local core organizers**, Rachel Heyard from the **Center for Reproducible Science at the University of Zurich** and Harini Lakshminarayanan **Open Innovation in Life Sciences Association**, for their on-the-ground coordination and unwavering support throughout the planning and delivery of the retreat.

We extend heartfelt appreciation to our sponsors:

- **Swiss National Strategy Council for Open Research Data**
- **SNSF Scientific Exchange Grant (No. 232539)**
- **Wikimedia CH Foundation**
- **Imming Impact**

With their support, we were able to both host fun and meaningful evening activities and offer **full or partial travel and participation stipends to 27 attendees**—making it possible for a broader and more diverse group to join us in the Swiss Alps.

Special shout-outs to those who went above and beyond: from the spontaneous yoga instructors and morning jog leaders to the impromptu DJs at the silent disco, the name tag crafters, social activity hosts, and every person who helped others feel welcome. You made this a retreat to remember.

We'll close with a sentiment shared in more than one feedback form:

"It was the people, the openness, and the vibe. I felt like I belonged."

We can't wait to see where this energy takes us—until #OSR26UK!

People who helped write this report

Wrote & edited the report: Joyce Kao, Harini Lakshminarayanan, Rachel Heyard, Heidi Seibold

Provided short summaries of unconference sessions: Julia Pauquet, Lisa Spitzer, Doaa Abdelkader, Gorca Fraga Gonzalez, James Bartlett, Danny Garside, Melanie Imming, Pallab Pradhan

Appendix

Useful links

- Open Science Retreat Series website:
<https://open.science-retreat.org/>
- Open Science Retreat 2025 Event website:
<https://events.digital-research.academy/e/OSR25CH>
- Full program:
<https://events.digital-research.academy/event/47/timetable/#all.detailed>
- A public participant list can be found here:
<https://events.digital-research.academy/event/47/registrations/participants>
- ResearchEquals Collection for 2025 Retreat outputs:
<https://www.researchequals.com/collections/k86g-wf>